

Activated carbons prepared from oil palm shells : application for column separation of heavy metals

Anuar Kassim*, Collin Glen Joseph, Zulkarnain Zainal, Mohd. Zobir Hussein, Md. Jelas Haron and Abdul Halim Abdullah

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Environmental Studies, University Putra Malaysia, 43400 UPM, Serdang, Malaysia

E-mail : anuar@fsas.upm.edu.my

Manuscript received 8 October 2002, revised 22 March 2004, accepted 26 May 2004

Physically and chemically activated carbons from oil palm shell, which is an agro-industrial waste, were prepared using CO_2 , H_3PO_4 , K_3PO_4 and KOH . A horizontal Carbolite Tubular Electric Furnace at a constant temperature of 500° for 4 h was used for pyrolysing and activating the oil palm shells in inert atmosphere. The activated carbons were ground into 500–1000 μm sizes prior to the packing. Separation of a mixture of 3 heavy metal ions, that is, Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} metal ions were carried out successfully. Two commercial activated carbons, AC 4050 and AC 7080, were used for comparative study. Comparisons of adsorption capacity at different pH and column chromatography studies were carried out in this study.

The presence of heavy metals in the environment is of major concern because of their toxicity and threat to human life and the environment. Anthropogenic sources of heavy metals include wastes from the electroplating and metal finishing industries, metallurgical industry, tannery operations, chemical manufacturing, mine drainage, battery manufacturing, leachates from landfills and contaminated groundwater from hazardous wastes sites. These contaminants must be removed and using activated carbons is one of the cheapest and easiest method. Literature survey indicates that there have been many attempts to obtain low-cost activated carbon or adsorbent from agricultural wastes such as *coconut shells*^{1–3}, *almond shells*^{4–8}, *peach stones*⁶, *grape seeds*⁸, *apricot stones*^{4,8–9}, *cherry stones*^{8,10}, *olive stones*^{5,6,11}, *peanut hull*¹², *nut shells*¹³, *rice husks*¹⁴, *resak wood*^{15,16}, *sugarcane bagasse*¹⁷, *Uruguayan eucalyptus wood*¹⁸, *Melaleuca cajuputi*¹⁹ and oil palm shells^{20,21}. A benefit often associated with activated carbon is the ability to preferentially attract one substance to its surface and to separate it from the rest of the system. Adsorption by activated carbon is an established treatment method for organic contaminants but has been rarely used in an actual treatment setting for inorganic adsorbates, despite the fact that the ability of activated carbons to remove heavy metals has been established by numerous researchers. Studies have shown that activated carbon is suitable to be used as packing material for column chromatography. Researchers have successfully used activated carbons to adsorb heavy metals from aqueous solution in column chromatography^{22–24}. In

this study, activated carbons were used as packing material for column chromatography to adsorb and separate heavy metal ions in a tri-component system.

Results and discussion

The adsorption capacities at different pH were studied for all the activated carbons to determine whether separation is possible for the mixture of metal ions solution. 10 ppm of each metal ion solution, Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} were used individually with different activated carbons to determine the adsorption capacity. Nitric acid with the pH 0 to 5 was used to determine the capacity at which the mixture metal ions can be separated and eluted in the column chromatography. Nitric acid with the pH 6 or higher is not suitable for adsorption capacity study because precipitations of the metal ions will occur. For separation to happen, the adsorption capacity at pH 0 to pH 5, for each metal ion, should not overlap with each other. If this happens, the activated carbon used, will only be able to adsorb the metal ions but it will not be able to separate the mixture of metal ions during the elution process in the column chromatography. Fig. 1, shows the adsorption capacity of AC 7080, AC 4050, AC H_3PO_4 and AC KOH respectively. AC 7080, AC 4050, AC H_3PO_4 and AC KOH have similar adsorption capacity patterns so it is possible to separate the mixture of metal ions by eluting mixture at different pH. Zn^{2+} will be eluted first at about pH 2, followed by Pb^{2+} at about pH 1 and finally by Fe^{3+} at about pH 0. The adsorption capacity pattern of AC PHY is different from other activated car-

bons. Pb^{2+} would be eluted first at about pH 2, followed by Zn^{2+} at about pH 1 and Fe^{3+} at about pH 0. With AC K_3PO_4 Pb^{2+} was eluted first at about pH 1, followed by Zn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} at about pH 0. pH 2 cannot be used to elute Pb^{2+} because it will also elute Zn^{2+} . These will be discussed in the column studies that were done using a mixture of Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} with the concentration of 100 ppm each.

Activated carbons in the column have a near neutral pH, at about pH 5.5. Distilled water was passed through the column until the flow rate was stable. After that, the mixture of metal ions was injected. This is because adsorptions of the metal ions by the activated carbon occur at about pH 6. Functional group OH^- in the activated carbon plays an active part in retaining the metal ion in neutral conditions and then when acid of different concentration was used for elution, the H^+ bonds with the OH^- expelling the metal ion. Nitric acid solutions of different pH were used to elute the sample for 10 fractions until 30 fractions are collected and analyzed for all 3 metals. In the first 10 fractions, the column was eluted with 0.01 M HNO_3 , in the second 10 fractions, the column was eluted with 0.1 M HNO_3 and finally in the last 10 fractions, the column was eluted with 1 M HNO_3 . The commercial activated carbons, AC 4050 and AC 7080 have large surface area therefore the separation of the metal ions were complete with Zn^{2+} being eluted first followed by Pb^{2+} and then Fe^{3+} . The AC H_3PO_4 has a lower surface area, therefore the elution curve shows that the Pb^{2+} ion was eluted earlier compared to the commercial activated carbons. For the AC KOH, although it has very low surface area, it is possible that the OH^- from the chemical activator used to impregnate the palm shells, helped to hold on to the metal ions and elute them in a similar pattern as the commercial activated carbon. The shifting of the Pb^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions are most pronounced in the AC PHY and the AC K_3PO_4 . This is because both of the activated carbons have very low surface area compared to the commercial activated carbons with smaller OH^- functional groups. The Fe^{3+} ion seems to form quite stable complex with the activated carbon, because it retains the same position at the last 10 fractions. Table 1 shows that the recovery of the metal ions was between 73 to 97%. This proves that column chromatography packed with activated carbons can be used to separate and recover metals in wastewater from industries.

Conclusion :

Activated carbon can be used as a packing material for column chromatography to separate metal ions. The column studies indicated that the activated carbons can be used to separate Zn^{2+} - Pb^{2+} - Fe^{3+} from a mixture. The data also indicated that OH^- functional group plays an important role

in the adsorption of the metal ions. The activated carbon packing has to be neutral or near neutral for adsorption to occur and acidic for elution to happen. Higher surface area activated carbon, AC 7080, has better separation capabilities compared to lower surface area activated carbon, AC K_3PO_4 . Although AC KOH has a lower surface area, it had better separation capabilities compared to AC PHY. This was possibly due to the hydroxide ions in the potassium hydroxide that was introduced as a chemical activator. The hydroxide ions bond with the metal ions during adsorption and release it during elution when the acidic eluent was passed through the column.

The data on the recovery of the metal ions showed that more than 70% of the metal ions were recovered. Therefore it is possible to conclude that activated carbons produced from oil palm shells are suitable to be used as packing material for column chromatography.

Experimental

There are two principal processes for the preparation of activated carbons : physical and chemical activations²⁵. For physical activation, the method used in this study, involves carbonisation or pyrolysis of the carbonaceous material, followed by activation of the resulting char at 500°C in the presence of suitable oxidizing gases such as carbon dioxide. For the chemical activations, the same methods were used in this study except that phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4), potassium phosphate (K_3PO_4) and potassium hydroxide (KOH) were used individually to impregnate the precursor, prior to the carbonisation process. These chemicals are dehydrating agents, which are capable of influencing pyrolytic decomposition and inhibiting formation of tar, thus enhancing the yield of carbon⁶. The physical and chemical properties for the activated carbons differ from one to the other due to the way they have been prepared²⁶. Therefore activated carbons prepared from a specific source may only be useful for a specific application.

In order to prepare activated carbons treated by phosphoric acid, AC H_3PO_4 , 30 g of the palm shells were mixed with 15 ml of H_3PO_4 and 100 ml of distilled water in a 250 ml conical flask. The concentration of the H_3PO_4 solution was 2.2 M². To prepare activated carbons treated by potassium phosphate, AC K_3PO_4 , 30 g of palm shells were mixed with 9 g of K_3PO_4 and 100 ml of distilled water in a 250 ml conical flask. The concentration of the K_3PO_4 solution was 9% (w/w) K_3PO_4 ²⁷. To prepare activated carbons treated by potassium hydroxide, AC KOH, 30 g of palm shells were mixed with 9 g of KOH and 100 ml of distilled water in a 250 ml conical flask. The concentration of the KOH solu-

Fig. 1. Adsorption capacity for AC 7080 : (◆) Pb, (■) Zn, (▲) Fe.

Table 1. The percentage of recovery of the Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions from column elution

Metal ions (%)	AC PHY (%)	AC H_3PO_4 (%)	AC K_3PO_4 (%)	AC KOH (%)	AC 4050 (%)	AC 7080 (%)
Zn	85.2	93.3	88.1	97.1	73.1	97.1
Pb	93.4	96.4	93.1	89.2	93.6	77.6
Fe	92.5	95.2	97.4	94.4	97.3	95.1

tion was 9% (w/w) KOH²⁷. Then the impregnations were carried out in an oil bath shaker at 70°C, for 24 h. The samples were dried at 120° overnight in an oven. In order to prepare the physically activated carbon, AC PHY, oil palm shells were not treated with any chemicals; it was just carbonized and activated in the furnace.

A horizontal Carbolite Tubular Electric Furnace was used for the carbonization and activation processes. The impregnated precursors were carbonized using N_2 gas at 500° for 3 h, followed by CO_2 gas for an hour at the same temperature. The activated carbons obtained were allowed to cool to room temperature before removal. This is to prevent the activated carbons from turning into ash. After that, the activated carbons were refluxed in an acid solution (1 M HNO_3), one time for 3 h to remove metal elements and ash followed by distilled water (10 times, 3 h each time) to remove the acid. The activated carbons were dried in an oven at 120° for a week, after which analysis of the activated carbons were done²¹.

Adsorption capacity of Pb, Fe and Zn at different pH :

Adsorption capacities of the activated carbons for the

selected metal ions were determined by using atomic absorption spectroscopy. 1 g of the activated carbon was put in an Erlenmeyer flask with 200 ml of different concentration of nitric acid that is from pH 0 to pH 5 containing 10 ppm of either Pb, Fe or Zn ion. The solution in the flasks were shaken for 4 h, and filtered. The metal ion content of the solution was determined with the atomic absorption spectrometer model Shimadzu AA-680.

Separation of metal ions using column chromatography :

1 g of activated carbon was packed in a column and attached to a peristaltic pump model Pharmacia Biotech Pump P-50 and fraction collector model Pharmacia Biotech GradiFranc with plastic tubes. Suitable eluent was passed through the column with a flow rate of 0.3 ml/min with fractions collected every 26 min. The volume in each fraction was exactly 7.8 ml. The amount of activated carbon used was 1 g and the length of the packing was 4.5 cm except for the AC KOH, which was 6.5 cm. The concentration of the tri-component solution (Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Fe^{3+}) was 100 ppm each. Fractions collected from the column

chromatography were analyzed using ICP-AES analyzer model Perkin Elmer-Emission Spectrometer Plasma 1000.

Acknowledgement

The authors are very grateful for the scholarship given to Collin Glen Joseph under Pasca Siswazah Scheme by Universiti Putra Malaysia.

References

1. Q. Mortley, W. A. Mellowes and S. Thomas *Thermochim. Acta*, 1988, **129**, 173.
2. J. Laine, A. Calafat and M. Labady *Carbon*, 1989, **27**, 191.
3. M. Razvigorova, M. Goranova, V. Minkova and J. Cerny, *Fuel*, 1994, **73**, 1718.
4. R. Torregrosa and J. M. Martin-Martinez, *Fuel*, 1991, **70**, 1173.
5. M. Domingo-Garcia, I. Fernandez-Morales, F. J. Lopez-Garzon and C. Moreno-Castilla, *Langmuir*, 1991, **7**, 339.
6. F. Rodriguez-Reinoso and M. Molini-Sabio, *Carbon*, 1992, **30**, 1111.
7. F. Guzel and Z. Tez, *Separation Sci. Tech.*, 1993, **28**, 1069.
8. K. Gergova, N. Petry and S. Eser, *Carbon*, 1994, **32**, 693.
9. C. A. Philip and B. S. Girgis, *J. Chem. Tech. Biotechnol.*, 1996, **67**, 248.
10. M. C. Lussier, J. C. Shull and D. J. Miller, *Carbon*, 1994, **32**, 1493.
11. M. T. Gonzalez, M. Molina-Sabio and F. Rodriguez-Reinoso, *Carbon*, 1994, **32**, 1407.
12. K. Periasamy and C. Namasivayam, *Separation Sci. Tech.*, 1995, **30**, 2223.
13. C. Nguyen, A. Ahmadpour and D. D. Do, *Adsorption Sci. Tech.*, 1995, **12**, 247.
14. L. B. Khalil, *Adsorption Sci. Tech.*, 1996, **13**, 317.
15. K. Anuar, G. J. Collin, B. H. A. Faujan, Z. Zulkarnain, M. H. Zobir and A. A. Halim, *Research J. Chem. Env.*, 2001, **5**, 3.
16. K. Anuar, G. J. Collin, B. H. A. Faujan, Z. Zulkarnain, M. H. Zobir and A. A. Halim, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 2002, **18**, 1.
17. B. S. Girgis, L. B. Khalil and T. A. M. Tawfik, *J. Chem. Tech. Biotechnol.*, 1994, **61**, 87.
18. N. Tancredi, J. Cordero, Rodriguez-Mirasol and J. J. Rodriguez, *Fuel*, 1996, **75**, 1701.
19. K. Anuar, A. Halim, Z. Zulkarnain, M. Z. Hussein, S. Hamdan and S. Wooi, *Ultra Science*, 2000, **12**, 355.
20. K. Anuar, G. J. Collin, Z. Zulkarnain, M. H. Zobir and A. A. Halim, *Malaysian J. Anal. Chem.*, 2002, (in press).
21. K. Anuar, G. J. Collin, Z. Zulkarnain, M. H. Zobir, Md. Jelas Haron and A. A. Halim, *ASEAN J. Sci. Tech. Dev.*, 2002, **2**, 149.
22. D. C. Sharma and C. F. Forster, *Biores. Technol.*, 1994, **47**, 257.
23. W. T. Tan, S. T. Ooi and C. K. Lee, *Environ. Technol.*, 1993, **14**, 270.
24. C. K. Lee, K. S. Low and K. L. Kek, *Biores. Technol.*, 1995, **54**, 183.
25. F. Rodriguez-Reinoso, "Science and Technology of Activated Carbon, Short Course", Universidad de Alicante, 1994, 4.
26. J. J. S. Mattson and H. B. Mark (Jr.), "Activated Carbon", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1971.
27. J. Laine and A. Calafat, *Carbon*, 1991, **29**, 949.
28. H. Jankowska, A. Swiatkowski and J. Choma, "Active Carbon", Ellis Horwood, England, 1991, 113.